

Analysis of Competitiveness and Obstacles of Bohai Rim Ports

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Abstract: As an important trade hub connecting Northeast and North China, the Bohai Rim Port Group has made significant contributions to promoting the economic development of the Bohai Rim region. This article constructs a new indicator evaluation system consisting of 17 indicators from five dimensions, including infrastructure, green development and etc. The subjective weighting of BWM and the CRITIC method based on cloud models are used for objective weighting, and the final weight is obtained by combining weighting. The TOPSIS method is used to evaluate the competitiveness of ports around the Bohai Sea, and the obstacle factors affecting the development of ports around the Bohai Sea are identified through the obstacle degree model. In the end, we divided the Bohai Rim ports into four categories.

Keywords: port competitiveness, TOPSIS, barrier factors,

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1. Introduction

As one of the five major ports, the port around Bohai Sea is not only located in the coordinated development area of Beijing Tianjin Hebei, but also the construction focus of the northern port of the "the Belt and Road". The research on the competitiveness of the ports around Bohai Sea is mainly carried out from the following aspects:(1) Research on port industry clusters and port city relations. Based on the theory of population ecology, Han Erdong adds the conditions that reflect the obstacles faced by port groups and term model, and constructed a more realistic nonlinear time delay model, providing a theoretical basis for the coordinated development of port industry clusters^[1]. Li Nan uses the Tapio decoupling model to explore whether urban development may be decoupled from port operations. They mainly used the main port cities in the Bohai Rim region as samples and concluded that Dandong and Qinhuangdao are currently in a decoupling state, while cities such as Tangshan and Rizhao are closely related to ports and have greater difficulty in decoupling^[2]. (2) Research on factors affecting port competitiveness. Huang Han and others select factors such as commodity import and export volume, cargo throughput, container throughput, and SO₂ emissions per unit of GDP to construct a competitiveness evaluation index system^[3]. Zhang Zhongkai and others consider the influencing factors of port competitiveness, including smart ports, green ports, etc., and constructed a new port competitiveness evaluation system that includes indicators such as port digitalization degree and unit GDP energy consumption^[4].(3) Research on

research methods for port competitiveness. Peng used the CCPE port competitiveness evaluation model to evaluate port competitiveness from four aspects, including port conditions^[5]. The weights of primary and secondary indicators were calculated using AHP and entropy weight method. From the literature review, it can be seen that current research on competitiveness is relatively mature. Considering the current requirements for high-quality development of ports, we have added indicators such as carbon emissions and comprehensive energy consumption per unit throughput to comprehensively and fully evaluate port competitiveness.

1. Establish an evaluation index system for port competitiveness

The port competitiveness evaluation system is an important link in constructing the competitiveness evaluation of ports around the Bohai Sea, providing corresponding basis for the evaluation of individual indicators and comprehensive capabilities of port competitiveness. There are two key points. Firstly, based on existing literature and the specific situation of the port, select indicators that are suitable and can reflect the research purpose, and construct an indicator evaluation system that is suitable for the port. Secondly, determine the appropriate indicator weight calculation method. This chapter improves the existing basic weight calculation methods and applies them to the corresponding calculation of port indicator weights. By reviewing references and consulting with experts, and considering the availability or computability of data, we ultimately selected a competitive evaluation index system for ports around the Bohai Sea with five dimensions and 17 indicators, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Evaluation Indicators for Competitiveness of Bohai Rim Ports

Target layer	Criterion layer	Indicator layer	unit	Indicator type
Port competitiveness (C)	Infrastructure (C ₁)	Number of 10000 ton berths (C ₁₁)	piece	B-O
		Total number of berths (C ₁₂)	piece	B-O
		Total length of dock berths (C ₁₃)	meter	B-O
	Production level (C ₂)	Cargo throughput (C ₂₁)	10000 tons	B-O
		Container throughput (C ₂₂)	10000 TEU	B-O
	Hinterland environment (C ₃)	Investment in fixed assets (C ₃₁)	Ten thousand RMB	B-O
		Per capita GDP of hinterland cities (C ₃₂)	RMB	B-O
		Total import and export goods (C ₃₃)	Ten thousand yuan	B-O
		The ratio of the tertiary industry to GDP (C ₃₄)	%	B-O
		Actual total utilization of foreign investment (C ₃₅)	Ten thousand US dollars	B-O
	Port development potential (C ₄)	Growth rate of cargo throughput (C ₄₁)	%	B-O
		Container throughput growth rate (C ₄₂)	%	B-O
		Growth rate of total import and export commodities (C ₄₃)	%	B-O

		GDP growth rate of hinterland cities (C ₄₄)	%	B-O
		Growth rate of fixed assets investment in transportation, warehousing and postal services in hinterland cities (C ₄₅)	%	B-O
	Green Development (C ₅)	CO ₂ emissions from ports (C ₅₁)	t	Cost based
		Comprehensive energy consumption per unit throughput (C ₅₂)	(tce/104t)	Cost based

Especially, B-O mains benefit oriented.

2. Evaluation model for competitiveness of ports around Bohai Sea

In the evaluation model, we subjectively calculate the expert score weights through BWM, use the CRITIC method based on cloud models to obtain objective weights, obtain combination weights through combination weighting, and finally use TOPSIS method to evaluate competitiveness.

2.1 Combining Weighting to Obtain Weights

2.1.1 Using the BWM method to obtain subjective weights

The Best Worst Method (BWM) is a problem which can determine the subjective weight of indicators. It selects the best (most important) and worst (least important) indicators from a series of indicators by experts or based on theory, and compares them with other indicators^[6]. Compared with Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), it can simplify the cumbersome process and improve reliability. The specific steps are as follows:

- ① Experts are asked to select the best indicator Y_B and the worst indicator Y_W from the indicator set.
- ② Experts determine the relative importance of the remaining indicators to Y_B by scoring them on a scale of 1 to 9 and obtain a comparison vector $C_B = (C_{B1}, C_{B2}, \dots, C_{Bj})$.
- ③ Determine the relative unimportance of the remaining indicators relative to Y_W and obtain a comparison vector $C_W = (C_{W1}, C_{W2}, \dots, C_{Wj})$.
- ④ Solve the optimal indicator weights based on the objective optimization model. The calculation formula is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min k \\ & s.t \begin{cases} \left| \frac{\omega_B}{\omega_j} - a_{Bj} \right| \leq k \\ \left| \frac{\omega_j}{\omega_w} - a_{jw} \right| \leq k \\ \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j = 1 \\ \omega_j \geq 0 \\ j = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Among these indicators: ω_B is the weight of C_B ; C_j is the criterion vector; ω_j is the weight of C_j , ω_W is the weight of C_W , a_{Bj} is the importance value of C_B for C_j , a_{jW} is the importance value of C_j for C_W .

⑤ Use k^* to represent the obtained k value and calculate the consistency ratio CR. The calculation formula is as follows:

$$C_R = \frac{k^*}{C_I}$$

At last, weighted average the weight coefficients of many experts(n) to obtain subjective weights. The calculation formula is as follows:

$$\omega_{sj} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^n \omega_j^m}{n}$$

2.1.2 CRITIC objective weight calculation model based on cloud model

In this article, the data is mainly collected into a cloud model. However, the traditional CRITIC method cannot meet the needs of calculating indicator weights under cloud model data. Therefore, we have used an improved objective weight calculation model: the objective weight calculation model of the CRITIC method based on cloud models. The initial evaluation matrix formed after standardizing the indicators, where is the evaluation value of the i-th scheme represented by the cloud model under the j-th indicator, the specific steps of using the CRITIC method to obtain objective weights are as follows:

① Using the reverse cloud generator, the data collection is aggregated into a cloud model. $y_{ji} = (Ex_{ji}, En_{ji}, He_{ji}), j = 1, 2, \dots, 11; i = 1, 2, \dots, 17$ as shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Part of Cloud model data of Bohai Rim ports

	Dandong Port	Dalian Port	yingkou port
C11	(0.7250,0.4825,0.0030)	(0.5278,0.2855,0.1124)	(0.7167,0.4261,0.0024)
C12	(0.4889,0.2005,0.1618)	(0.5840,0.2888,0.0937)	(0.7182,0.4033,0.0027)
C13	(0.6518,0.3268,0.1263)	(0.5576,0.3105,0.0850)	(0.7222,0.4123,0.0020)
C21	(0.5424,0.3973,0.0007)	(0.5516,0.3423,0.0024)	(0.5584,0.4031,0.0019)
C22	(0.5140,0.4022,0.0020)	(0.7362,0.3274,0.1140)	(0.5135,0.3109,0.0235)
C31	(0.3679,0.4164,0.0014)	(0.3521,0.4849,0.0023)	(0.3625,0.4467,0.0017)

② Calculate the correlation coefficient between two indicators:

$$\rho_{jk} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m d(x_{ij}, \bar{x}_j)d(x_{ij}, \bar{x}_k)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (d(x_{ij}, \bar{x}_j))^2 \sum_{i=1}^m (d(x_{ij}, \bar{x}_k))^2}}$$

Among them, $j, k=1, 2, n$ and d represent the distance between the clouds formed by two indicators, \bar{x}_k and \bar{x}_j represent the mean evaluation values under the k-th and j-th indicators, respectively:

$$\bar{x}_j = \frac{1}{m} \times \sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}; (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

③ Calculate the information content indicator C_j for each attribute indicator:

$$C_j = \sigma_j \sum_{k=1}^n (1 - \rho_{jk}); (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

Among them, σ_j is the standard deviation of the evaluation value under the j -th attribute:

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (d(x_{ij}, \bar{x}_j))^2}; (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

④ Calculate the objective weight of each attribute indicator based on information content:

$$\omega_{oj} = \frac{C_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n C_j}; (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

2.1.3 Combination weighting

Finally, use the combination weighting formula to calculate the subjective and objective weights that have already been calculated, and obtain the final combination weight:

$$\omega_j^* = \frac{\omega_{sj} \omega_{oj}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \omega_{sj} \omega_{oj}}$$

2.2 Construction of Combined Weighting TOPSIS Evaluation Model

The TOPSIS method is a common comprehensive evaluation method, which mainly involves calculating the comprehensive distance between alternative solutions and the optimal and worst ideal solutions. If a solution is closer to the optimal ideal solution and further away from the worst solution, which has a higher degree of closeness, it is considered better. The specific steps are as follows:

① Establish the initial decision matrix from the previous text X' .

② Calculate the weight of indicator combination

③ Find positive and negative ideal solutions. In this article, we choose the maximum value of each indicator as the positive ideal solution E_j^+ and 0 as the negative ideal solution E_j^- .

④ Calculate closeness. For the i -th scheme E_{ij} , we calculate its distance L_i^+ from the optimal solution and the distance L_i^- between the worst solution separately:

$$L_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j^* (E_j^+ - E_{ij})^2}$$

$$L_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j^* (E_j^- - E_{ij})^2}$$

Among them, ω_j^* is the combination weight calculated in the previous text. Finally, calculate the closeness of the competitiveness evaluation indicators for each port:

$$T_i = \frac{L_i^-}{L_i^+ + L_i^-}$$

Using the calculated closeness as the quantitative evaluation result. We analyze the level of port competitiveness based on the degree of closeness, and the greater the closeness, the higher the competitiveness of the port.

3 Empirical research

3.1 Obtaining Combination Weights

According to the previous BWM and cloud based CRITIC methods, the subjective and objective weights were calculated separately. The combination weights were obtained using the combination weighting formula, as shown in Table 3:

Table 3: Weights of Bohai Rim port portfolios

Index	BWM method	CRITIC method	Combined weight
Total number of 10000 ton berths C ₁₁	0.0936	0.2417	0.2787
Total number of berths C ₁₂	0.155	0.1502	0.2868
Port terminal length C ₁₃	0.1039	0.0858	0.1098
Cargo throughput C ₂₁	0.1113	0.0268	0.0367
Container throughput C ₂₂	0.1162	0.0637	0.0912
Investment in fixed assets C ₃₁	0.0211	0.0412	0.0107
The actual amount of foreign investment used in the current year C ₃₂	0.0164	0.0398	0.0080
Per capita GDP C ₃₃	0.0369	0.0277	0.0126
Total import and export volume C ₃₄	0.0148	0.0269	0.0049
The proportion of the tertiary industry to GDP C ₃₅	0.0183	0.0153	0.0034
Growth rate of cargo throughput C ₄₁	0.0358	0.0394	0.0174
Container throughput growth rate C ₄₂	0.0422	0.0252	0.0131
Growth rate of total import and export C ₄₃	0.0377	0.0322	0.0150
GDP growth rate C ₄₄	0.0341	0.0333	0.0140
Growth rate of fixed investment in transportation, warehousing, and postal services C ₄₅	0.03025	0.0582	0.0217
Carbon emissions C ₅₁	0.0647	0.0321	0.0256
Comprehensive energy consumption per unit throughput C ₅₂	0.0678	0.0604	0.0504

3.2 Calculating closeness

According to formulas above, the closeness of the Bohai Rim port is obtained, and the results are shown in Table 4, which can reflect the actual situation of the Bohai Rim port:

Table 4: Results of the 2021 TOPSIS assessment

port	L_i^+	L_i^-	T_i	sort
Dandong Port	0.3928	0.8309	0.3210	10
Dalian Port	0.5737	0.4962	0.5362	3
Yingkou port	0.4557	0.5940	0.4341	6
Jinzhou Port	0.3885	0.9255	0.2957	11
Qinhuangdao Port	0.4236	0.6711	0.3870	7
Huanghua Port	0.4324	0.7608	0.3624	9

Tangshan Port	0.5675	0.5258	0.5191	4
Tianjin Port	0.7565	0.4330	0.6360	2
Yantai Port	0.4759	0.5648	0.4573	5
Qingdao Port	0.7682	0.4175	0.6479	1
Rizhao port	0.4149	0.6690	0.3828	8

3.3 Analysis of evaluation results

According to the 2021 TOPSIS evaluation results, it can be seen that the ranking order of each port is: Qingdao Port, Tianjin Port, Dalian Port, Tangshan Port, Yantai Port, Yingkou Port, Qinghuangdao Port, Rizhao Port, Huanghua Port, Dandong Port, and Jinzhou Port. The higher the closeness, the better the evaluation result. We can divide ports into the following categories based on their proximity: the first category is Tianjin Port and Qingdao Port, which have a very obvious leading advantage compared to other ports. In 2021, the container throughput of the two ports was 20.27 million TEU and 23.71 million TEU, respectively, and their hinterland cities also have distinct characteristics; The second category includes Dalian Port, Tangshan Port, Yantai Port, and Yingkou Port, which are at a moderate level but still have some room for improvement; The third category is Rizhao Port, Huanghua Port, Dandong Port, and Jinzhou Port, which have insufficient overall competitiveness.

From Table 3, it can be seen that the top three influencing factors for the weight ranking of game theory combinations are: the number of berth per 10000 tons, the total number of berth, and the length of port terminals. At the same time, the dimension of green development (including carbon emissions and comprehensive energy consumption per unit throughput) has a relatively small proportion in the combination weight of game theory. Whether from a subjective or objective perspective, the role of green development in measuring port competitiveness is weaker than other dimensions such as infrastructure, which indirectly reflects the insufficient emphasis on green development factors at present and requires further understanding.

3.4 Obstacle analysis

Diagnosed and analyzed the top five obstacle factors that affect the competitiveness of ports around the Bohai Sea in 2021, obtained the impact of each indicator on port competitiveness, and drew a hotspot map based on the results. As shown in Table 5 and fig 1:

Table 5: Barriers to port competitiveness

port	project	Indicator sorting				
		1	2	3	4	5
Dandong Port	O	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₂₂	C ₂₁
	D	26.26%	17.83%	11.15%	9.54%	5.69%
Dalian Port	O	C ₂₂	C ₁₁	C ₄₁	C ₃₁	C ₄₅
	D	16.67%	10.35%	9.89%	9.02%	8.97%
Yingkou port	O	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₂₂	C ₄₅
	D	20.02%	15.88%	9.05%	8.75%	5.82%
Jinzhou Port	O	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₂₂	C ₂₁
	D	25.92%	18.64%	11.05%	8.60%	5.01%
Qinghuangdao	O	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₂₂	C ₁₃	C ₅₂
	D	23.01%	14.51%	10.03%	9.04%	8.46%
Huanghua Port	O	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₂₂	C ₃₂
	D	26.62%	19.33%	11.61%	10.39%	4.39%

Tangshan Port	O	C ₁₂	C ₂₂	C ₄₅	C ₅₁	C ₃₂
	D	18.05%	16.32%	13.12%	9.81%	5.78%
Tianjin Port	O	C ₅₂	C ₄₅	C ₅₁	C ₁₂	C ₄₃
	D	25.46%	17.81%	11.57%	11.46%	6.25%
Yantai Port	O	C ₂₂	C ₄₅	C ₅₂	C ₁₁	C ₅₁
	D	18.20%	13.42%	11.01%	10.73%	6.25%
Qingdao Port	O	C ₁₂	C ₁₁	C ₄₅	C ₅₁	C ₁₃
	D	25.80%	21.46%	15.06%	10.16%	10.10%
rizhao port	O	C ₁₂	C ₁₁	C ₂₂	C ₁₃	C ₃₁
	D	19.78%	18.72%	10.72%	9.30%	6.07%

In the table5, O mains :Obstacle factor; D mains obstacle degree

Fig. 1 Heat map of port competitiveness barriers

From Table 5, it can be seen that the competitiveness barriers of ports around the Bohai Sea in 2021 (frequency ≥ 3) are ranked as follows: total number of 10000 ton berths, total number of berth, length of port terminals, container throughput, fixed investment growth rate of transportation, warehousing and postal industry, carbon emissions, and comprehensive energy consumption per unit throughput. Among them, the total number of 10000 ton berths, total number of berth, and container throughput rank high, indicating that the degree of infrastructure construction and production level have a significant impact on the evaluation of port competitiveness. The competitiveness barriers of Qingdao Port include the total number of berth, the total number of berths with a capacity of 10000 tons, and the growth rate of fixed investment in transportation, warehousing, and postal industries, indicating that Qingdao Port needs to pay attention to continuous progress in these factors.

4. Summary

This article uses BWM and cloud based CRITIC methods to assign subjective and objective weights respectively, and combines them with TOPSIS method to comprehensively rank and analyze the competitiveness of ports around the Bohai Sea in 2021. We can divide ports into the following categories based on their proximity: the first category is Tianjin Port and Qingdao Port, which have a very obvious leading advantage compared to other ports; the second category includes Dalian Port, Tangshan Port, Yantai Port, and Yingkou Port, which are at a moderate level but still have some room for improvement; the third category is Rizhao Port, Huanghua Port, Dandong Port, and Jinzhou

Port, which have insufficient overall competitiveness. Through obstacle analysis, the obstacle factors affecting the development of ports around the Bohai Sea are identified, providing a basis for further development of ports around the Bohai Sea.

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